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(ICRTB 2024)

January 19-20, 2024

ABSTRACTS

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PP-041

Development of an enzyme inhibition-based optical biosensor for the detection of Hg²⁺ using paper-based platform

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Abstract: In the present work, an enzyme inhibition-based biosensor was developed to detect Hg²⁺ using a functionalized cellulose paper platform. Acid phosphatase (ACP) sourced from *Macrotyloma uniflorum* seeds exhibited pronounced inhibition in the presence of Hg²⁺. The assay reagent, a blend of α -naphthyl phosphate, aromatic diazonium ion and a polymer matrix, was applied to a patterned paper with circular reaction zones. Hydrolytic cleavage of the substrate resulted in the formation of a chromogenic diazo complex, imparting a reddish-pink colour to the paper substrate. Pre-treatment of the enzyme with Hg²⁺ led to its inactivation, thereby hindering the release of naphthol and causing a reduction in the colour intensity of the paper probe. The diminished colour intensity correlated with an elevated concentration of Hg²⁺, establishing the biosensor as a viable tool for Hg²⁺ detection. The developed sensor exhibits simplicity, robustness, and cost-effectiveness, rendering it suitable for application in constrained laboratory settings or resource-limited conditions. Furthermore, the potential for future applications in environmental monitoring and point-of-care diagnostics underscores the significance of this innovative biosensor.

Keywords: Paper-based analytical devices, enzyme inhibition, acid phosphatase, biosensor, Hg²⁺

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ISBN 978-93-6039-051-8

